

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP3 – Determination of drug transfer and infant drug exposure during lactation: generation of quantitative and translatable data

D3.5 In vivo data on lactation transfer in one or more animal species

Lead contributor	Domenico Ventrella (5 - UNIBO) domenico.ventrella2@unibo.it
Other contributors	Maria Laura Bacci (5 – UNIBO) Camilla Anibaldi (5 - UNIBO) Alberto Elmi (5 – UNIBO) Monica Forni (5 – UNIBO) Michele Bouisset-Leonard (38 – NVS) Anthony DeLise (38 – NVS) Patrick Devine (38 – NVS) Nurit Ashkenazi (51 – Teva) Lilach Steiner (51 – Teva) Kirsten Jacobsen (49 - Ellegaard) Mie Johanne Hansen (49 - Ellegaard) Yeghig Armoudjian (20 – Bionotus) Johan Van Daele (20 – Bionotus) Pieter Annaert (7 – KUL) Brian Anderson (50 – Covance)

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	29 Mar 2022	Draft
V2.0	11 Apr 2022	Final Version

Abbreviations

EDTA	Ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid
Ga	Gauge
ID	Identification
IM	Intramuscular
IV	Intravenous
LLOQ	Lower limit of quantification
NSAID	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs
PBPK	Physiologically based pharmacokinetic
PD	Pharmacodynamics
PK	Pharmacokinetic
SEM	Standard error of the mean
SID	Semel in Die (Latin: Once A Day)
ULOQ	Upper limit of quantification
WP	Work package

Content

Document History.....	2
Abbreviations.....	3
Content.....	4
Abstract	5
Methods.....	6
1.1 Animals	6
1.2 Training.....	6
1.3 Long-term catheter insertion.....	7
1.4 Study design and amoxicillin dosing.....	8
1.5 Samplings.....	9
Results	10
Discussion	14
Conclusion.....	16

Abstract

The aim of task 3.3 of the ConcePTION project is to develop and characterise a relevant *in vivo* model for drug passage from maternal blood to human breast milk. The chosen species to perform such non-clinical trial was the porcine one, as reported in the Deliverable 3.2 of the same project. In the initial trial, amoxicillin was chosen as the first molecule for a variety of reasons including alignment with other Work Packages (WPs) performing studies on human breastmilk. Additionally, since amoxicillin is commonly used in pigs, the choice of the route of administration, the administration interval and the doses were supported by reliable background data. Six sows were used for this amoxicillin trial: 3 conventional commercial hybrids and 3 Göttingen Minipigs. The trial started at the beginning of the second week of lactation and lasted up to piglets weaning (28 days after birth). Sows were administered IM with 7mg/kg of amoxicillin (SID) for the entire duration of the trial; on the first day a PK analysis was performed to check the consistency with literature data. For the rest of the trial, sampling days were divided into “sow days”, consisting of 4 matched blood/milk samples, and “sow+piglets days”, consisting of 2 matched milk/blood samples from the sow plus blood from 4 piglets (2 piglets sampled before amoxicillin and 2 piglets sampled 30 minutes after sows’ sampling). To quantify amoxicillin, samples were frozen, shipped on dry ice and analysed by BioNotus. Amoxicillin was always quantifiable in sows’ samples: the highest plasmatic concentrations were recorded 2h after dosing, while the highest milk concentrations 4h after. Out of the 136 blood samples collected from piglets, only 9 showed amoxicillin levels above the detection limits. The latter finding, along with the recorded milk peak at 4 hours after administration, seems to suggest the need for additional sampling time points for piglets. Overall, the study design used for this initial amoxicillin trial has allowed to highlight both strengths and critical points of this new *in vivo* platform to test infant drug exposure through milk. The procedures were feasible and well tolerated by animals that gained confidence and trust during the preliminary training sessions. This is extremely important when assessing the overall ethical impact of the trials.

Methods

1.1 Animals

The preliminary trial for Amoxicillin was performed at the University of Bologna on a total of 6 sows: 3 conventional hybrids and 3 Göttingen Minipigs. As previously stated, conventional pigs were included for several reasons, including the experience of the research team with such breeds, the usually higher litter size and the volume of collectable samples. Conventional pregnant sows were purchased from a local farm, SUIMAX di Massimo Ferri (Via San Michele 718, Valsamoggia 40056 BO, Italy), chosen based on the microbiological status of the facility and for the reproductive track records. Göttingen Minipigs pregnant sows were provided by Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs (Soroe Landevej 302 4261 Dalmoose, Denmark), which contributed as breeding facility within the project framework. All piglets included in the study were born from the above-mentioned sows in the experimental facility of the ANFI-ASA Unit, Department of Veterinary Medical Sciences, Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna (via Tolara di Sopra 50, Ozzano dell'Emilia 40064 BO, Italy). Sows were transferred to the experimental facility 1 month prior the expected delivery date (calculated based on the insemination/mating date and ultrasound pregnancy scan) and moved to the farrowing pen one week before. Animals were checked at least twice a day for health status. Farrowing was not pharmacologically induced, as this often leads to complications, but remotely assisted by trained veterinarians.

Animals were fed a standard diet according to the breed: Basic Micropigs (9AB17) by Mucedola s.r.l. (Settimo Milanese 20019 MI, Italy), which is specialized in dedicated formulas for lab animals exclusively used for experimental purposes; while commercial sows received a formula specifically made for breeding animals, produced by a local vendor (Molini Popolari Riuniti, Ellera-Umbertide 6019 PG, Italy). Both feeds were in the form of pellets, since its production process is suitable for preserving the organoleptic and hygienic characteristics of the product for a long time (24 months from the date of production). Drinking water was provided *ad libitum*, while the daily feed ratio was divided into two portions, early morning (7:30 am) and afternoon (3:30 pm); feed total amount was adjusted during the course of lactation, to cope with the considerable metabolic energy expenditure of the sows. Light/dark cycle was set at 12/12h with a min Lux value during light hours of 40. Temperature was set at $21 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ to meet sows thermal needs. With regards to piglet, two heat lamps were placed in dedicated areas of the farrowing crate to reach $32 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Piglets were individually identified with ear tags, and iron dextran (100mg) was administered IM within the first 72h of life.

1.2 Training

A key factor for the success of *in vivo* trials is animals' behavior, that can be shaped through the consistent use of positive reinforcement training, also fulfilling the 3Rs principle for animal welfare.

Clicker training, first described for dogs, is accepted worldwide as one of the most effective methods for teaching basic obedience to different animal species and to direct their intelligence toward productive and positive activities. It has been adapted to numerous other species, including pigs. The method is based on positive reinforcement, precisely with the association of the double-click sound produced by a specific device, with a reward, such as a tasty snack or a toy. One of the biggest challenges in pig training, especially when looking at conventional animals, is getting the animals to trust the operator and understand that no harm is involved. This is also why, alongside microbiological evaluations, it is important to select a supplier with extremely high welfare standards. Once they understand the training session entails no distress, it becomes a welfare enrichment itself. When transferred to the experimental facility, pregnant sows (both conventional and Minipigs) were gradually accustomed to the trainers, first by just introducing a human presence in the room with food rewards; these first acclimatization steps were short (just few minutes) but were done daily, to build trust and a bonding relation. As a positive reinforcement, animals were given a food reward (apple slices, apple juice and yogurt were always very welcome). After the first week, trainers started to approach the animals: pregnant sows were gradually accustomed to follow the trainers and being manipulated especially at the level of mammary glands and ears. Training sessions were short (20 min) but consistent and repeated daily (Monday-Friday). After some repetitions, the action-click-reward association became a conditioned stimulus that could keep the animals motivated to accomplish different tasks while having fun in the meantime. As demonstrated by previous studies, swine positive emotions could be indicated by play, barks and tail movements, while negative behavior is suggested by freezing, defecating/urinating, escape attempts, high-pitched vocalizations and ear movements. During the training sessions all the animals showed well-being associated activities, and, after the routine was established, they were easily manipulated and seemed to enjoy the training session, an additional occasion to get out of the cage and explore the environment.

1.3 Long-term catheter insertion

Towards the end of the first lactation week, conventional and Minipig sows were deeply sedated by an intramuscular injection (Tiletamine/Zolazepam 3.5-5 mg/kg; Zoletil 50/50 Virbac srl) for the peripheral insertion of a long-term catheter through an auricular vein. Oxygen was provided during the procedure through a breathing mask. During the entire duration of the procedure, which always lasted less than 60 min, support fluid therapy (Ringer Lactate 10 ml/kg/h) and the usual anaesthesia monitoring were provided (ETCO₂, SpO₂, Temperature, ECG, NIBP).

Catheterizations were performed following standard surgical sterility guidelines: clipped, neat, disinfected area dedicated, sterile surgical draping, gloves and instruments (packed and autoclaved for each animal); surgical field prep consisted of 3 alternating scrubs of a chlorhexidine scrubbing solution and 70% alcohol. Ear veins (*v. auricularis caudalis* or *v. auricularis intermedia*) are suitable for this kind of IV long term access, despite course, branching and size can differ dramatically from

animal to animal. Seldinger's over-the-wire technique was employed for peripheral auricular vein catheterization: the vessel was punctured with a dedicated sharp hollow needle which was then removed with the plastic sheath left in place to allow the guidewire to be advanced through it for at least 30mm. Once the wire was inserted without major resistance, the sheath was removed and replaced with a vessel dilator. Finally, upon dilator removal, the catheter was slid over the wire and into the vein, sutured to the skin and further fixed by means of an IV securement dressing integrated with chlorhexidine gluconate gel pad (Tegaderm CHG, 3M). Heparinized saline (300IU/ml) was used as lock solution to ensure patency on a daily bases and after every blood collection. Catheter sets were purchased by Mila International: MILACATH Guidewire (SA1925) - Single Lumen - 19Ga (3.5Fr) x 25cm (10in) for Göttingen Minipigs sows; MILACATH Guidewire (SA1420) - Single Lumen - 14Ga (6Fr) x 20cm (8in) with integrated extension set, for commercial breed sows.

1.4 Study design and amoxicillin dosing

On the first day of the trial, sows were administered IM with 7mg/kg of amoxicillin (Clamoxyl® RTU; Pfizer) and a PK analysis was performed. A total of 11 blood samples were collected:

- Before amoxicillin administration
- 30min after administration
- 60min after administration
- 90min after administration
- 2h after administration
- 3h after administration
- 4h after administration
- 5h after administration
- 6h after administration
- 12h after administration
- 24h after administration

For the remaining 3 weeks of lactation, sows were always administered IM 7 mg/kg of amoxicillin (SID); injection were performed at the common preferred area for adult pigs, just behind the base of the ear, alternating the side every day. Animals were distracted and rewarded with food during injection, which was quick. Sows' weights were recorded at least once a week to adjust amoxicillin dosage.

The trial was structured as follows:

- SOW DAY: 4 matched milk/blood samples (before amoxicillin, 2, 4 and 8h after); twice a week

- SOW+PIGLET DAY: 2 matched milk/blood samples (before amoxicillin and 2h after) from the sow plus blood from 4 piglets (2 before amoxicillin and 2 piglets 30 minutes after sows' sampling); twice a week.

date	I19			I20			I21		
	post partum	lactation week	procedure	post partum	lactation week	procedure	post partum	lactation week	procedure
13/04/2021							farrowing		
14/04/2021	farrowing						P1		
15/04/2021	P1			farrowing			P2		
16/04/2021	P2			P1			P3		
17/04/2021	P3			P2			P4		
18/04/2021	P4			P3			P5		
19/04/2021	P5		Cat	P4		Cat	P6		Cat
20/04/2021	P6			P5			P7		
21/04/2021	P7	amoxi	PK	P6	amoxi	PK	P8	amoxi	PK
22/04/2021	P8	amoxi	Sow	P7	amoxi		P9	amoxi	Sow
23/04/2021	P9	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P8	amoxi	Sow	P10	amoxi	Sow+Piglets
24/04/2021	P10	amoxi		P9	amoxi		P11	amoxi	
25/04/2021	P11	amoxi		P10	amoxi		P12	amoxi	
26/04/2021	P12	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P11	amoxi	Sow	P13	amoxi	Sow+Piglets
27/04/2021	P13	amoxi	Sow	P12	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P14	amoxi	Sow
28/04/2021	P14	amoxi		P13	amoxi		P15	amoxi	
29/04/2021	P15	amoxi	Sow	P14	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P16	amoxi	Sow
30/04/2021	P16	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P15	amoxi	Sow	P17	amoxi	Sow+Piglets
01/05/2021	P17	amoxi		P16	amoxi		P18	amoxi	
02/05/2021	P18	amoxi		P17	amoxi		P19	amoxi	
03/05/2021	P19	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P18	amoxi	Sow	P20	amoxi	Sow+Piglets
04/05/2021	P20	amoxi	Sow	P19	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P21	amoxi	Sow
05/05/2021	P21	amoxi		P20	amoxi		P22	amoxi	
06/05/2021	P22	amoxi	Sow	P21	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P23	amoxi	Sow
07/05/2021	P23	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P22	amoxi	Sow	P24	amoxi	Sow+Piglets
08/05/2021	P24	amoxi		P23	amoxi		P25	amoxi	
09/05/2021	P25	amoxi		P24	amoxi		P26	amoxi	
10/05/2021	P26	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P25	amoxi	Sow	P27	amoxi	Sow+Piglets
11/05/2021	P27	amoxi	Sow	P26	amoxi	Sow+Piglets	P28	amoxi	Sow
12/05/2021	P28	amoxi		P27	amoxi				
13/05/2021				P28	amoxi	Sow+Piglets			

Figure A. Trial calendar for the Göttingen Minipigs sows.

1.5 Samplings

Blood samplings from sows were carried out relatively easily due to the previously described training: animals, distracted by the food reward and accustomed to being touched on the ears, did not care about the operator collecting blood from the catheter. The latter allowed for a pivotal refinement of the study as no pain was involved in this procedure. Yet it has to be acknowledged how commercial sows occasionally showed mild aggressive behavior aimed at protecting the litter; this issue was never encountered with Göttingen Minipigs sows. Blood was collected into EDTA tubes, upon elimination of the residual lock solution within the catheter lumen together with the first ml of blood to avoid contamination. Right afterwards, the catheter was flushed with saline solution and locked again with heparinized saline. The procedure was always performed by two operators, one in charge of providing the animal with the reward (usually apple juice) and the second working on the catheter. Samples were immediately centrifuged (15min, 1800rcf, 4°C) to obtain plasma, which was divided into 500µl aliquots and stored at -80°C.

To avoid excessive stress in piglets, blood was collected from the femoral artery upon light sedation achieved by means of Sevoflurane administered through a breathing mask in 100% O₂. In order to allow for the potential amoxicillin present in milk to be absorbed into piglets' bloodstream, the samplings were actually performed 30 min after maternal samplings (that always coincided with

nursing).

As for milk samples, the procedure was much more challenging, since the ejection period is very short in pigs and happens only upon intense stimulation of the udder by the litter. Considering the operators would have to wait for the piglets jostling and nuzzling on the mammary glands to induce oxytocin release, pivotal for milk ejection, the research team decided to administer sows with exogenous oxytocin (10-20 IU, IM). This allowed for more precise samplings in terms of timing as matched blood/milk collection was required for this preliminary study. Milking was performed manually, as fast as possible, and directly along the length of the sow's nipple; indeed, massaging the udder does not allow for a good sampling and, as of today, no commercial mechanical devices are available for the chosen species. During the collection of the milk samples, piglets were not separated from the sow, therefore the operators had to compete with the litter to access a teat. Fortunately, piglets tend to establish a preference for a given nipple during the first lactation days, and only aim at that one when nursing. This allowed the operators to know, for each sow, where to collect from. Milk samples were immediately placed on ice, aliquoted as for plasma and stored at -80°C. At the end of the 6 trials, samples were shipped on dry ice to Bionotus for amoxicillin quantification.

Results

During the trial, it was always possible to easily access the ear catheter and the mammary glands for blood and milk collection, respectively. Despite the vulnerable post-partum period, sows have always maintained cooperative behavior towards the trainers, even when piglets were momentarily removed to perform the blood sampling.

Unfortunately, during the first day of dosing and PK samplings, one of the Göttingen Minipigs sows (ID: I20) became severely lethargic and hyperthermic. The animal was immediately treated with NSAIDs (Flunixin Meglumine, 2.2mg/kg) and IV fluid therapy (Lactated Ringer, 5 ml/kg/h) and strictly monitored; metoclopramide (0.3mg/kg IM) was administered since gastric motility seemed stopped, with negative auscultation, anorexia and failure to defecate. Ellegards' veterinarians were consulted to confirm the correct therapeutic approach. X-ray and ultrasound scans revealed a severe gastric dilation potentially due to overfeeding, thus a gastric washing under general anesthesia (Proposure® 4mg/Kg) was performed. The sow fully recovered within 24 hours and never stopped nursing. However, to avoid potential biases to the trial and results, the sow only re-entered the trial one week after (P15, at the third lactation week). Nonetheless, amoxicillin administration was never interrupted so that the samplings would resemble the ones performed in the other animals.

The results of the bioanalytical assays performed to quantify amoxicillin in both plasma and milk along with the analyses validation and methodology can be found in Bionotus report from Armoudjian Y.

and Lin Q. (Appendix 1; Determination of Amoxicillin in Pig Plasma and Milk using LC-MS/MS; 2021). The lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) was 10 ng/mL, the upper (ULOQ) 10000 ng/mL.

The following tables and graphs represent the averaged data of both conventional and Göttingen Minipigs sows, as no significant differences were recorded between breeds. Generally speaking, amoxicillin was always above the quantification limits in sows' plasma and milk, with the expected exception of the first plasma sample (collected before the first amoxicillin dosing). This finding confirms that amoxicillin is consistently able to cross the blood/mammary barrier into milk.

The PK analyses performed on sows on the first dosing day are represented in **Figure B** (data from I20 were excluded due to the complications during the PK day, see above). At T_{max}, the mean plasmatic amoxicillin concentration was 1.44 µg/ml. Amoxicillin was also quantifiable in plasma 24h after dosing, although in very low concentrations (mean 0.097 µg/ml).

Figure B. Plasma PK of amoxicillin (7mg/kg IM, SID) in conventional and Göttingen Minipigs sows on the first day of dosing. Histograms represent the mean; error bars represent the SEM (standard error mean).

Descriptive statistics for the quantification of amoxicillin into maternal plasma and milk samples are reported in **Table 1** and **2** respectively.

Table 1. Amoxicillin quantification ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) in maternal plasma samples.

	<i>n</i>	Min $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Max $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Mean $\mu\text{g/mL}$	SEM $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Before administration	65	0,014	1,849	0,295	0,034
2h after administration	65	0,274	4,977	1,351	0,090
4h after administration	34	0,259	2,349	0,998	0,074
8h after administration	32	0,218	1,726	0,785	0,058

n indicates the number of samples

Table 2. Amoxicillin quantification ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) in maternal milk samples.

	<i>n</i>	Min $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Max $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Mean $\mu\text{g/mL}$	SEM $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Before administration	56	0.012	2.039	0.125	0.037
2h after administration	65	0.014	1.607	0.217	0.037
4h after administration	32	0.010	2.583	0.290	0.083
8h after administration	31	0.026	0.390	0.153	0.019

n indicates the number of samples

When looking at amoxicillin concentrations in sows matched blood/milk samples collected before administration, 2, 4 and 8h after, the trends differ between the matrices (**Figure C**). Indeed, the highest plasma concentrations were recorded 2h after IM amoxicillin administration, while the highest milk concentrations were 4h after. For plasma, all experimental time points statistically differed between each other (Kruskal-Wallis test, Conover post-hoc test; $p < 0.0001$); as for milk, all the time points after administration statistically differed from the pre-administration one (Kruskal-Wallis test, Conover post-hoc test; $p < 0.0001$), but not between each other. The results of the statistical evaluations are indicated by different letters in **Figure C**.

Figure C. Amoxicillin concentrations (µg/mL) in sows’ plasma and milk samples at the four experimental time points. Different letters indicate statistically relevant differences ($p < 0.05$). Histograms represent the mean; error bars represent the SEM (standard error mean).

Out of the 136 blood samples collected from piglets, only 9 showed amoxicillin levels above the quantification limits (LLOQ 10 ng/ml, ULOQ 10000 ng/ml): five were collected before maternal dosing and four 2h afterwards (**Figure D**). Thus, no inferential statistical evaluation was performed.

Figure D. Scatter plot of the individual values of amoxicillin ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) recorded into piglets plasma.
 LLOQ: 10ng/ml; ULOQ: 10000ng/ml.

Nonetheless, when comparing the milk samples collected 2 hours after amoxicillin administration and the corresponding piglets' plasma, the difference seems to suggest that, at this time point, piglet exposure to drug in milk is low and not detectable with the developed method (**Figure E**). It is important to remember that piglet's plasma was collected 30 min after milk sampling to allow potential absorption in the bloodstream.

Figure E. Amoxicillin levels in sows' milk and piglets' plasma collected 2h after maternal dosing. Histograms represent the mean; error bars represent the SEM (standard error mean).

Discussion

The aim of this first lactation study was to assess if the swine species, selected upon extensive literature review (see deliverable D3.2), could effectively be used to build an *in vivo* lactation model able to provide quantitative and translatable data. Additionally, this preliminary study was necessary to assess the feasibility of the procedures, as little to no data are available with regards to milk collection in pigs. This preliminary study included conventional hybrid sows, that could never be used in the pharma setting for different reasons such as drug quantities and facility requirements, mainly due to the expertise and experience with these porcine breeds of the UNIBO research team. Despite the logistical challenges in working with animals weighing up to 300kg, large hybrid sows showed good maternal behavior, from time to time even excessive, to the point of showing aggression towards very well know trainers, especially in the first two weeks after delivery. However, conventional hybrid piglets are usually more numerous and bigger than Minipigs, thus blood collection was relatively easier and allowed for higher volumes of samples. Therefore, the UNIBO team performed the first trials on conventional sows, before moving to Göttingen Minipigs, to have a substantial feeling of what

was actually feasible looking at both the researchers' and the animals' points of view. Another "strength" of conventional sows was the bigger ears size, with many vessels, making for easier and faster catheter insertion procedures. Working with a "large" animal model species, the Göttingen Minipigs, allows for more extensive samplings, both in terms of volume and frequency of collection, leading to many future possibilities to further characterize the model itself. Pigs are relatively easy to train and get accustomed to human interaction in a short amount of time when the correct training procedures are applied; accordingly, sows were successfully clicker-trained with a food reward to be approached and touched on the ears (for blood sampling) and the abdominal region (for milk collection). The main refinement to the experimental procedures, along with the above-mentioned training, was the placement of a peripherally inserted central venous catheter (from an auricular vein) for repeated blood sampling. This allowed the researchers to collect blood samples without inflicting any pain to the sows while a second operator distracted them with a food reward. When looking at piglets' samplings, catheter placement was not feasible due to their size, but blood was collected under deep sedation achieved by Sevoflurane administered through a breathing mask. For every time point, only 2 piglets, selected in rotation within the litter, were sampled, allowing to minimize repeated sedation and stress. This is why individual identification of piglets was extremely important. For this preliminary trial, the research team decided not to collect any sample from the animals (sows and piglets) during the first week of lactation, to grant colostrum ingestion and maternal-offspring bonding and behavior. Despite this potentially representing a major flow to a "final" study design, as data regarding colostrum may be extremely important, it was important for this preliminary trial to start gradually and include procedures that seemed feasible based on the research team experience. Additionally, also ConcePTION WP4, working with human breastmilk, is avoiding colostrum to ensure that lactation is well established and minimize the differences in quantity of drugs in milk that would be linked to the differences in composition between colostrum and milk.

Amoxicillin was chosen as the "model" molecule for this preliminary trial for several reasons. First of all, it is one of the molecules that will be used by ConcePTION WP4 for a clinical study. Therefore, by the end of the project, the consortium will be able to compare *in vivo* data from both breastfeeding mothers and lactating sows. Additionally, amoxicillin is widely used for therapeutic purposes in porcine medicine, thus some background pharmacological data in the chosen species was already available. Such experiences allowed for a better prediction of potential side/adverse effects, deemed extremely low, thus giving the research team the chance to precisely analyse the ethical costs/benefits ratio and to focus on the study design and feasibility. The study design was technically feasible and well tolerated by the sows and the piglets. Animals did not show any discomfort-related behavior during the sampling procedures and the entire duration of the trial. Therefore, the research team will apply the same study design for the other model compounds to be tested (venlafaxine, levocetirizine and metformin), with some anticipated modifications in terms of timing of samples that will be tailored according to the existing PK/PD data in the porcine species.

As for the quantification of amoxicillin in the different matrices, the results are consistent between sows, even when comparing the different porcine breeds used. The plasmatic peak reached within 2 hours after IM administration is in line with existing literature. No background data were available for milk, yet the peak in its amoxicillin concentration was similar between animals and for the entire duration of the study (3 weeks). The lack of existing literature and data regarding infant exposure to amoxicillin through milk makes the interpretation of the piglets' results hard and only inferential. Indeed, the "absence" of amoxicillin in the vast majority of piglets' plasmatic samples may be explained by several factors potentially related to the study design and/or the analytic technique. From the study design point of view, now that data regarding milk concentrations are available, it looks like collecting piglets' blood at the 4h nursing may have provided different results. Therefore, this additional sampling time for piglets will be implemented in the amoxicillin trials that will be performed later in the project by the CRO Labcorp Drug Development (former COVANCE). Doing so will allow the research group to better understand the PK of amoxicillin transfer into milk and potential uptake into nursing piglets.

Conclusion

Overall, the study design used for this preliminary amoxicillin study has allowed to highlight both strengths and critical points of this new *in vivo* platform to test infant drug exposure through milk. The procedures were feasible and well tolerated by animals that gained confidence and trust during the preliminary training sessions. The availability of *in vivo* milk/plasma data will allow for detailed comparison with *in vitro* data generated for the same species, enabling to gain increased confidence in the *in vitro-in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) algorithms that can subsequently be translated to the human situation via PBPK modelling. The high-resolution of *in vivo* lactation data in Minipigs along with *in vitro* data obtained for the same model compounds in pig mammary epithelial cells (currently ongoing) will be instrumental to improve and refine generic templates and workflows for PBPK-based prediction of drug milk excretion in human.